

Acknowledgement

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References

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Decarboxylation of Oxamic Acid in Resorcinol and Catechol

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CLARK¹ has made extensive studies on the decarboxylation of oxamic acid in several non-aqueous solvents. Oxamic acid decarboxylates in resorcinol and catechol in a manner similar to that of oxanilic acid². No kinetic data have been reported for the decarboxylation of oxamic acid in these solvents.

Experimental

Reagents: Oxamic acid used was an analytical reagent grade, m.p., 212°. Resorcinol and catechol were BDH analytical reagents. No further purification of these chemicals was done.

Apparatus and technique: The kinetic experiments were conducted in a constant temperature oil-bath ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) by measuring the volume of CO₂ gas evolved at constant pressure. The apparatus and technique are the same as described in our previous articles^{3,4}. 0.1586 g of oxamic acid was taken in about 50g of resorcinol and 50 g. of catechol separately and allowed to decompose in a constant temperature oil-bath. The CO₂ gas was collected at room temperature in a measuring burette filled with water which had been previously saturated with carbon dioxide.

Results and Discussion

The decarboxylation of oxamic acid was studied at seven different temperatures. The log (V_∞ - V_t) vs t, plot resulted in a straight line in all the experiments indicating that the reaction is of first order, where V_∞ is the maximum volume of CO₂ after complete decomposition and V_t is the volume at time t. The rate constants were calculated from the slopes of the graphs and are tabulated in Table 1. The Arrhenius parameters of Eyring equation based upon the data of Table 1 are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 1—FIRST-ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE DECARBOXYLATION OF OXAMIC ACID IN RESORCINOL AND CATECHOL.

Temp °C	No. of data pairs	Av. k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹ Resorcinol	Av. k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹ Catechol
140	3	2.57 ± 0.01	1.82 ± 0.02
145	4	4.57 ± 0.01	3.31 ± 0.03
150	5	8.71 ± 0.02	6.03 ± 0.01
155	4	15.49 ± 0.01	9.57 ± 0.03
160	3	26.31 ± 0.02	13.38 ± 0.04
165	2	42.66 ± 0.04	28.84 ± 0.05
170	2	75.87 ± 0.05	48.98 ± 0.05

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS.

Solvents	Resorcinol	Catechol
E _a kcal mole ⁻¹	38.95 ± 0.2	35.97 ± 0.2
log A (sec ⁻¹)	17.05 ± 0.01	15.27 ± 0.02
ΔH [‡] (kcal mole ⁻¹)	38.14 ± 0.3	35.14 ± 0.4
ΔS [‡] (cal mole ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹)	+13.30 ± 0.3	+10.12 ± 0.3
ΔF [‡] (kcal mole ⁻¹)	31.06 ± 0.2	31.62 ± 0.5
k ₁ × 10 ⁴ (sec ⁻¹) at 160°	26.31	13.38

The decarboxylation of oxamic acid is kinetically first order in both the solvents at the run temperatures of this investigation and the reaction is faster in resorcinol than in catechol, like other carboxylic acids²⁻⁵. No such abnormal behaviour has been observed as shown by oxanilic acid² in these solvents. It has been reported earlier that the single hydroxyl group of resorcinol associates with the carbonyl group of the acid while the other hydroxyl group remains isolated. In catechol the acid associates with the two adjacent, hydroxyl groups of catechol. Hence the bulkier intermediate complex in catechol than in

Fig. 1